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Interim Activity & Management Report (Periodic Technical Report - Part B)

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Based on Digital Fabrication

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CONTENTS

List of abbreviations.....	5
Definition	6
1. Project Progress Overview	6
1.1. Objectives	6
1.2. Explanation of the work carried per WP.....	7
1.2.1 Workpackage 1: Engagement & Community Growth.....	8
1.2.2 Workpackage 2: Pilot Open Solutions	13
1.2.3 Workpackage 3: Platform & Tooling	15
1.2.4 Workpackage 4: Evaluation & Impact Assessment	20
1.2.5 Workpackage 5: Dissemination & Outreach	23
1.2.6 Workpackage 6: Legal & Ethical Aspects	28
1.2.7 Workpackage 7: Project Management.....	31
1.2.8 Workpackage 8: Ethics Requirements.....	34
1.3. Impact.....	35
2. Update on the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results.....	35
3. Update of the data management plan	36
4. Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous reviews	36
5. Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2	36
5.1. Tasks	36
5.2. Use of resources.....	36
5.3. Overview of Person-months	40
5.3.1. Overview of Person-months for WP1	42
5.3.2. Overview of Person-months for WP2	43
5.3.3. Overview of Person-months for WP3	44
5.3.4. Overview of Person-months for WP4	46
5.3.5. Overview of Person-months for WP5	47

5.3.6. Overview of Person-months for WP6 48

5.3.7. Overview of Person-months for WP7 49

6. Summary and Outlook..... 50

7. Annex 52

List of figures

Figure 1: Made4You programmatic approach.....	7
Figure 2: Overview workpackages	8
Figure 3: Careables Meetups	11
Figure 4: Overview of events & engagement activities	11
Figure 5: Co-designed careables (Tricycle, Stomanoir, Open lights for wheelchair) ..	14
Figure 6: Co-design documentation of careables platform	16
Figure 7: careables general website.....	17
Figure 8: Welder app for documenting and sharing of careables.....	18
Figure 9: Social Business Model Canvas for Careables.....	25

List of tables

Table 1: Summary of results WP1	12
Table 2: Summary of results WP2	14
Table 3: Summary of results WP3	18
Table 4: Summary of results WP4	21
Table 5: Summary of results WP5	26
Table 6: Summary of results WP6	30
Table 7: Summary of results WP7	33
Table 8: Summary of results WP8	35
Table 9: Person-Month Status Table	37
Table 10: Total number of person-months (planned and reported for Month 18) ..	40
Table 11: Overview Person-months WP1	42
Table 12: Overview Person-months WP2	43
Table 13: Overview Person-months WP3	44
Table 14: Overview Person-months WP4	46
Table 15: Overview Person-months WP5	47
Table 16: Overview Person-months WP6	48
Table 17: Overview Person-months WP7	49

List of abbreviations

AGILE	Agile Heap EV
DDMP	Distributed Design Market Platform
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering
KUL	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
MAKEA	Makea Industries GmbH
OPEN	Opendot Srl
TOG	Fondazione Together To Go Onlus
WAAG	Stichting Waag Society
WEV	Wevolver Ltd
WP	Workpackage
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation GmbH

Definition

Careable - a careable is an open solution that aims to improve the quality of life for people with unmet needs or facing physical limitations. Careables are co-designed, replicable, accessible, adjustable, and shareable online, using digital technologies. Careables is a new category that promises readily customized solutions and a horizontal and collaborative approach to health and care.

1. Project Progress Overview

This is the mid-term progress report including month 1 till month 18 of the Made4You project. It gives an overview of the work carried out and the projects results achieved during the reporting period.

1.1. Objectives

The specific objectives for the project, as defined in the contract, are to:

- Connect existing communities of makers, engineers and fabricators with communities of citizens (including patients) and healthcare professionals;
- Co-design open healthcare solutions for citizens facing physical disablements, and for healthcare professionals to improve the healthcare services they provide;
- Improve access for citizens to grassroots healthcare solutions via co-design methods and open standard documentation, and provide them the tools to become active innovators;
- Establish a wide user-base open and dedicated platform to share and exchange open healthcare solutions as well as co-design experiences;
- Collect available existing solutions and make them more accessible via open standard documentation on the platform.

In order to reach these objectives Made4You defined a programmatic approach based on four pillars: pilot open solutions, tools & platform, community engagement & growth, and dissemination & outreach (see Figure 1 below). While these four pillars

represent are represented by the four workpackages (WP1-3 and WP5) the workplan in addition includes four supporting workpackages (WP4, WP6-8) that are equally important in contributing to achieving relevant project results.

Figure 1: Made4You programmatic approach

1.2. Explanation of the work carried per WP

In the following we will present the progress and interim results of each of the workpackages. While this report follows the suggested structure of discussing each workpackage individually we would like to stress that the work in Made4You is very much interlinked and spanning across different workpackages.

The work plan consists of 8 workpackages in total, which are interrelated in the following way: WP7 (Project Management), WP6 (Legal & Ethical Aspects) and WP8 (additional ethics requirements; added as an EC request) set the operational frame and guidelines for the activities in the other WPs. WP1 (Community Engagement & Growth) and WP5 (Dissemination & Outreach) work closely together to gain momentum for the project, while WP2 (Pilot Open Solutions) and WP3 (Platform & Tooling) are specifically dealing with the local support of co-design as well as the technical support structures for documenting and sharing open DIY healthcare solutions. WP4 (Evaluation & Impact Assessment) takes the role of overseeing the project from an evaluation perspective and collects evidence of the potential impact.

Figure 2: Overview workpackages

1.2.1 Workpackage 1: Engagement & Community Growth

Lead partner: WAAG

Contributing partners: ZSI, OPEN, GIG, AGILE, WEV, KUL, TOG

The aim of this work package is to engage stakeholder communities, bring these existing communities together and connect them in the field of open source healthcare solutions. The engagement focuses on both local level as well as global engagement activities.

From the onset WP1 teamed up with WP5 to establish a working group that coordinates the community building and communication activities in a structured way. The outcome of the joined activities of this team was a detailed communication and engagement strategy, which has been reflected in the deliverables D1.1 and D5.1.

In terms of engagement and community building the first project year was regarded as experimental. The three Fab Lab partners, namely WAAG, OpenDot and Fablab Berlin, tested different methods and formats to connect local communities and get them engaged in discussions and actions on open healthcare. It was also the start of co-design sprints (see WP2), which again were executed in different arrangements across the labs.

The experiences with informal first get-togethers, mostly in the form of MeetUps and Open Days, was intensively reflected in the consortium as the responses were quite different across the labs, who all experimented with slightly different formats and approaches to get local communities engaged.

Engagement activities in the Netherlands started with a first informative event, such as an Open Day event at the maker space or a workshop at a museum, to generally address the issue of open DIY healthcare participants were engaged in design sprints. Teaming up with a hospital resulted very fruitful in the case of WAAG, where first ideas for careables were generated early on. After a first series of events it became clear that the co-design process takes more time than expected. A 2,5 hours session on a weekday evening proved to be too short and so the time allocated to the sessions was expanded and moved to Saturdays. During this first reporting period WAAG organized a series of informal awareness raising events and 3 intense co-design sprints.

In the case of the FabLab Berlin the first Meetups were arranged to start building the local community and getting a feeling for the co-creation needs. Initially, groups of people were working on different senses (seeing, feeling, hearing, smelling, tasting). However, this distinction according to senses did not prove to be useful as many solutions relate to more than one sense and cognitive aspects would still not be reflected. A topic of great interest was mobility, including wheelchairs and prostheses. Teaming up with other initiatives was very successful in the Berlin case. A hackaton on hearables was organized together with a project conducted by Fraunhofer, which aims at the development of DIY hearing aids. Based on these first

experiences the FabLab Berlin joined forces with Match My Maker and Universities to establish the HackAdemy, a training event spanning across 3 weekends where participants receive training on co-creation, design thinking, digital fabrication, etc. and work together on DIY healthcare products.

While TOG focused on healthcare professionals and representatives of organizations working in the field of disability with specific events, Opendot in Milano targeted the maker community with Meetups, who showed great interest at the beginning. However, it resulted difficult to keep them engaged for a longer period as volunteering requires serious commitment and free time to dedicate to the development of careables. The initial Meetups were called “Hackability@Milano” in collaboration with Hackability, a no-profit organization focusing on the topics of accessibility and making and then from September on “Careables Meetup”. The format foresaw a talk at the beginning, followed by the specific case e.g. of visually impaired people and their needs, exemplified by one representative of an association. After some ideation phase the co-creation was done in 2 sessions and ended in the reshaping of the end of the cane, which can be reprinted for better resistance. Due to the facts that co-design required an intensive engagement on the side of the makers and the meet-up format is not popular in Italy, it became clear that some compensation for the makers was required and makers were featured in the local newsletter of the lab.

However, alternative approaches and the experiences from the other cities also led to some re-design of the engagement strategy. In April 2019 OpenDot launched Careables on air, that is both an event and a podcast with a knowledge-sharing scope: to present people and projects that are changing the healthcare sector. The co-creation between people facing physical limitations and makers/designers was instead experimented during the Health&Care Summer School, an intensive training course of 2 weeks about design for care. The Summer School was set up as a cooperation between the “DDMP – Distributed Design Market Platform” initiative and Careables.

Figure 3: Careables Meetups

It is important to stress the learning which took place in the first year on how to engage local communities in all three cases. As a result, in Berlin and Milan there has been a shift in the second year to address different audiences via different offers. One of the most promising activities currently are educational activities, such as the Hackademy in Berlin or the training offered to healthcare professionals in the case of Milano.

At global scale activities were closely aligned with WP5 in terms of communication and spreading the word. An initiating maker gathering around re:publica 2018, workshops at international events, such as re:publica Berlin, Chaos Communication Congress, re:publica Accra, Fab14 Conference, and the activities in the partner organisations of GIG in the global South contributed to a global awareness and engagement in open DIY healthcare. In addition, the development of platform for documenting and sharing careables is crucial for a global motivation. Thus, WP1 efforts were also dedicated to continuously feeding back on the platform design.

Figure 4: Overview of events & engagement activities

Summary of main achievements WP1:

Table 1: Summary of results WP1

results	indicator of achievement	key lesson
Success in creating a narrative and spreading that (raising awareness) via presentations	60+ presentations reported, broad range of topics that were covered	People agree with the relevance but still hard to truly mobilise institutions that aren't formally connected to the project already.
Successful combination of local open day and open calls	50 open days 40 workshops 12 maker gatherings 4 open calls	engagement has been achieved gradually and is a long process; makers, although motivated, have a limited time to spend for free; it is important to connect with existing local structures. Training is an important motivational factor.

There have been no major deviations from the original project plan (Annex 1) for WP1 and no major delay in the submission of the deliverable D1.1.

Outlook WP1 (planned activities for M18-M36):

In the city of Milan the planned activities will focus on two main target groups:

1. **University students** with presentations of Careables project in the main universities and two courses on design for care at NABA - Nuova Accademia di Belle Arti starting in November 2019;
2. **healthcare professionals** in collaboration with TOG with open days and courses on digital fabrication technologies.

Creating careables (WP2) will be also one of the suggested topics for the next Fabacademy at Opendot and is planned to contribute to the community building.

Berlin will continue to implement a HACKademy, based on the learning from the previous two events, teaming up again with a university or educational organisation.

In addition, in collaboration with the OpenNext project, there are plans to support careables producers with an incubation-type experience.

In Amsterdam the activities will continue to team up with healthcare professionals, such as hospitals, and strengthen the established collaborations. An important event for community building will also be the Design4 Health event, which is co-organised by WAAG and where we will launch further engagement activities.

Within the GIG hubs, activities to pilot open solutions (WP2) are the vehicle for community involvement. In July we started in Kumasi Hive and Nepal Communitere who also will open the first Fablab in Nepal in January 2020. Further collaborations with members of the ASK network and with hubs in South America are scheduled to begin in December 2019. Other hubs who connect their initiatives to Careables are Science Camp in Basra and Engineering Good in Singapore.

1.2.2 Workpackage 2: Pilot Open Solutions

Lead partner: AGILE (former MAKEA)

Contributing partners: ZSI, WAAG, OPEN, GIG, WEV, TOG

This workpackage aims at co-designing and piloting open source healthcare solutions. These solutions will serve as the primary actual content to be integrated into the online platform.

Activities in this WP were going on in parallel. On the one hand, co-design sessions as a result of the initial engagement activities (as described above in WP1) led to a series of truly bottom-up co-designed careables. While the co-design process itself was very successful and brought forward a set of very valuable healthcare solutions, the documentation process was experienced as difficult at the beginning. Valuable feedback for the improvement of the documentation tool (WP3) was gathered and stepwise realized. Important lessons learned were also gathered in terms of how to set up and organize a co-design process for open healthcare solutions. WP1 and WP2 worked closely together in this process and the groups shared their experiences continuously within the consortium and documented it in a co-design toolkit.

Figure 5: Co-designed careables (Tricycle, Stomanoir, Open lights for wheelchair)

On the other hand, partners performed a screening of existing open healthcare solutions and started documenting those on the careables platform as. Based on the first Open Healthcare Map (Deliverable D2.1), which includes a basic taxonomy in order to classify the careables, a detailed analysis of the proposed solutions led to a selection of careables across the different categories of our taxonomy.

The taxonomy itself is the outcome of another important activity of WP3, namely the analysis of existing taxonomies and the scanning of online repositories for open healthcare solutions. In a mapping process the open healthcare solutions were aligned with the different taxonomies and finally the solutions and the taxonomy underwent a loose evaluation within the consortium, reflecting on the usefulness and applicability from different angles (mostly a maker`s perspective and a healthcare professional`s perspective).

There have been no major deviations from the original project plan (Annex 1) for WP2 in terms of the work carried out and no major delay in the submission of the deliverable D2.1. However, there was an important contractual change. The initial organization leading WP2, MAKEA, left the project at the end of the first year and was replaced by a new organization, Agile Heap. The persons involved in the project, however, remain the same. Agile Heap took over the staff members working in the project and thus continuity for the project has been secured.

Summary of achievements WP2:

Table 2: Summary of results WP2

results	indicator of achievement	key lesson
Taxonomy of healthcare solutions	9 categories (mobility, careware, fun/leisure, daily living, therapy, self care, indoor installation,	We started from healthcare categorization of assistive devices rather

	outdoor installation, learning/communication)	than a maker-oriented taxonomy taking into account our target groups.
Co-design of local solutions	58 new solutions created	Highly individualized solutions provide rich lessons learned and inspire, generalizable solutions are more directly replicable.
Design sessions	HACKademies, Health&care Summer school Co-design sessions with students (TOG/OpenDot)	Short format for co-design events has proved to be more effective in terms of outputs and efforts from participants, in Berlin and Milan. Co-design is a process that needs to be guided by tools/templates.

Outlook WP2:

In the next 18 months we will shift the focus on the aspects of replication, as well as on strategies for parametric creation and adaptation of solutions. Here we prefer to rely on FLOSS (free libre and open source) tool chains for maximal accessibility and will create use-flows for various user groups.

For the co-design and replications we will also look for external cooperations, such as the Fablab in Zagreb, which already expressed their interest to pilot our approach.

1.2.3 Workpackage 3: Platform & Tooling

Lead partner: OPEN

Contributing partners: WAAG, GIG, AGILE, WEV, TOG

This work package focuses on re-designing, adapting and populating the Made4You platform, which is called “careables” and via is accessible www.careables.org

As outlined in Annex 1 of the contract, this workpackage started with the wevolver platform as a baseline to create careables.org, which we envision to be the preferred platform, all over the world, to find and create open, inspiring healthcare solutions and methods, transferable to local contexts by 2025. The necessary adaptations that were made in various iterations during the first project period have been informed by various inputs:

- First, an analysis of currently existing platforms with documentation tools and their current shortcomings was performed,
- second, a co-design session was held within the consortium during a meeting in Eindhoven; for the co-design session external experts from the open healthcare field were invited and allowed us to expand our views beyond the consortium partners.
- Third, we collected important feedback for the adaption of the platform during the careables co-design and training sessions that were conducted in the partner's maker spaces (see WP2 description above).

Figure 6: Co-design documentation of careables platform

Based on this diverse feedback various iterations of the platform were created and continuously discussed and tested. Most importantly the documentation tool has been completely redesigned in order to better meet the needs of the future users and make documenting as easy as possible. During the course of the first year

wevolver took the decision to split the wevolver platform and offer an open source version, namely welder.app. This open source platform forms now the basis for the documentation of careables open healthcare solutions.

Also, the main entry point for the users, the careables.org Wordpress website has been designed from scratch and is undergoing some important changes in order to make the user experience for the different target groups appealing.

The current version of the platform offers information on the project itself, it has a knowledge base, where we offer our resources, such as training material and co-design guidelines to specific target groups as well as events and other relevant knowledge related to open healthcare. From the main site users are directed towards the welder.app, where they can explore or share their own DIY open healthcare designs. We are currently working on creating more content for the careables website and e.g. considering adding a tutorial to the knowledge base of the project website as documentation is crucial for project to being replicated.

To summarize, we would like to stress that the platform is composed of different elements. The two most important parts to distinguish for the work in WP3 are:

1. careables.org is the main website and entry point hosted on Wordpress. It has both a knowledge-sharing and inspirational scope. A first initial version was launched in April 2018 and formed the basis for further co-design activities coordinated by Opendot. A second release is planned for autumn 2019.

Figure 7: careables general website (1st & 2nd design)

2. welder.app is based on the wevolver platform and is the repository of careables. Its creation and the development of the documentation tools were the main activities during 2018 and first part of 2019. The objective was to have

a database of documented solutions online in June 2019 and start to engage our targets groups.

Figure 8: Welder app for documenting and sharing of careables

There have been no major deviations from the original project plan (Annex 1) for WP3 in terms of the tasks performed. However, the real efforts for the development and adaptation of the platform have exceeded the expected efforts. This is due to the unexpected variety of the feedback received for the co-design of the platform and the high efforts that needed to be spent on the complete remake of the documentation tool. Due to all the efforts that we put into the platform development we experienced no major delay in the submission of the deliverable D3.1.

Summary of achievements WP3:

Table 3: Summary of results WP3

results	indicator of achievement	key lesson
Baseline map	26 mapped platforms	The existing online ecosystem of both tools and makers of health is wider than expected: from technical platforms to social collaborative environments.
Personas sheet and user journey map	Interviews and surveys	We identified 5 personas: caregiver, care recipient, maker, healthcare professional and institution representative.
Careables.org	1st release 2nd release on 1st October 2019	Both the definition of users and the co-design session in Eindhoven led to a radical reshaping of the platform structure: its objectives, identity, sections
Documentation tool	Version 1 on Wevolver Version 2 on Welder	Documenting is crucial and an issue: we went to a simplification of language and structure considering all our 4 target groups and we introduced 2 formats (1 pager/full documentation)
Open DIY health solutions	106 solutions on Welder.app (44 fully documented and 62 1-pager)	We are collecting valuable feedback about documentation tool from people using welder.app: students, participants in careables

		activities and makers.
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Outlook WP3:

The planned activities for M18 - M36 are:

- user-tests on Careables.org involving individuals representing our different target groups (healthcare professionals, caregiver, care recipient, maker and people interested in the topic of design for care) held in different countries;
- iterative implementation of Careables.org in terms of features/navigation/design following the user-tests up to the final release;
- iterative implementation of the documentation tool following the co-design sessions foreseen in WP2 and Open Calls in WP1;
- standardisation of the documentation tool thanks to the collaboration with Open Know-How initiative.

1.2.4 Workpackage 4: Evaluation & Impact Assessment

Lead partner: ZSI

Contributing partners: WAAG, OPEN, GIG, AGILE, WEV, KUL, TOG

The main aim of this work package is to ensure that Made4You platform and the open personalised healthcare solutions are accurate and consistent with the planned objectives set out by the project and according to the real needs of the involved stakeholders – people with disabilities, makers, health professionals and citizens. A second aim is to provide evidence for the envisioned impact and present alternative facts and stories to demonstrate the projects influence beyond the borders of the consortium.

In this work package we started off with the elaboration of an evaluation plan that helps to generate important formative feedback for the project activities as well as summative evaluation on the general careables approach. In order to collect evidence for both types of evaluation, formative and summative (impact assessment), we designed a set of instruments for data collection and provided templates for partners that can also be adapted to the local contexts. Local adaptation can be very important in our setting as healthcare is something very personal and users might relate more to their personal needs in their own language and according to the personal cultural setting.

An important step for the drafting of the evaluation plan was the prioritization of objectives towards impact measurement. During the consortium meeting in Eindhoven all partners engaged in reflecting on the overall project objectives as these have been rather widely defined. As outlined in the deliverable D4.1 the consortium jointly decided that the most important objective for the project is to improve the accessibility of open source products, followed by knowledge exchange support and the establishing of collaborations across communities (see D4.1 for details).

With the first activities taking place in WP2 we also started our continuous collection of evidence from the different project activities. The analysis of the collected data and insights coming from the project partners are continuously fed back to the consortium. In our weekly online meetings we reflect on the experiences made by the project partners and the feedback we receive from the participants in our activities.

A first important insight gained from these reflections was the fact that we shifted our engagement activities in the maker spaces from MeetUps and networking sessions more towards training-related activities as these seem to be more attractive to our target groups. The analysis of the interactions taking place in the maker spaces also reveal that the collaboration between patients and makers/designers needs to be mediated appropriately, roles and responsibilities need to be defined and collaboration processes clearly negotiated from the onset.

There have been no major deviations from the original project plan (Annex 1) for WP4 and no major delay in the submission of the deliverable D4.1.

Summary of achievements WP4:

Table 4: Summary of results WP4

results	indicator of achievement	key lesson
Evaluation framework defined	Deliverable submitted at time	Evaluation and impact assessment in this practical field of application is a complex process, thus we need a set of evaluation instruments that can be applied in different

		contexts and collect meaningful data from involved stakeholders
Evaluation of the Hackademy I	<p>10 questionnaires from participants</p> <p>6 questionnaires from facilitators</p> <p>8 user journey interviews</p> <p>4 interviews on drivers & barriers</p>	We learned about the main drivers and benefits of participating in the Hackademy, as well as the barriers encountered during the co-design work. Lessons learned concerning the timing, organisational support, motivations and outcomes feed the development of Hackademy II
Evaluation of the Health & Care SummerSchool	9 questionnaires from participants	Comparable to the Hackademy, we learned about the main motivational drivers/barriers and benefits for the diversified participants. The lessons learned concerning the timing/format, organisation etc. will feed further planning of engagement activities.
Evaluation of the MakeHealth Prototyping Serie	14 questionnaires from participants	The Makehealth Prototyping Serie is the format for a long-term involvement, thus it revealed again insights on motivational drivers/barriers and benefits of this type of

		intervention. The feedback is fed back to the organisational team to further improve the concept.
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Outlook WP4:

In WP4 we are currently working on the evaluation of the Hackademy II, where the lessons learned from Hackademy I were integrated into a new format and organisational support. This allows us to see in how far the participants' feedback changed between the two formats. We are also consolidating this feedback with the feedback from the MakeHealth Prototyping Serie and the OpenDot Summer School to come up with consolidated lessons learned from our engagement activities and their impact on participants. To grasp the long-term effects of the user- engagement activities we will also get in contact with participants from our three formats several months after their engagement via interviews.

Concerning the continuous platform evaluation, we will involve users in our pilot sites in extended user acceptance testings and get involved in the analysis of usage patterns on the platform, as soon as the new version of Welder is launched extensively in the community.

1.2.5 Workpackage 5: Dissemination & Outreach

Lead partner: GIG

Contributing partners: ZSI, WAAG, OPEN, AGILE, WEV, KUL, TOG

This work package aims to address different stakeholders to raise awareness for the project and, more generally, on the topic of open and personalised healthcare solutions. Its objective is also to disseminate the results of the project widely in order to ensure adoption of the solutions offered on careables.org, finding alliances and defining a strategy for the sustainability of the project results.

WP5 established a close collaboration with WP1 from the very beginning of the project to define a common communication strategy. Basically, the strategy is set up in three phases, moving from a local focus in terms of outreach and engagement

during the first year to a more global perspective in the second project year and shifting the focus towards sustainability in the third year. Another important input for the communication strategy was the stakeholder mapping and defining different strategies on how to address them. More details can be found in D5.1.

During the first 18 months of the project all partners were heavily engaged in dissemination activities and the project had a strong presence in many dissemination events, such as conferences and workshops, as well as smaller presentations in front of specific target audiences in addition to the targeted engagement events described in WP1. A detailed list of all events attended and/or organized by the project partners is available in the Annex.

In parallel to our physical presence in relevant events we also established our digital presence. The careables social media channels on Twitter, Facebook and Instagram were activated and have already started to gain the attention of a growing audience. Our Twitter account has grown to almost 250 followers, and on Facebook we currently reach around 300 organic (= non paid) followers. Careables online visibility is also growing due to the partners strong online media presence and cross-referencing. E.g. The wevolver platform and social media feeds is reaching over 6 Million people per month. Careables benefits from this wide outreach and will do so more in the next project period, where more dedicated online promotion is planned.

Another important set of activities during this first half of the project is related to networking and starting alliances with other projects or initiatives. Some examples where we have established working relationships with e.g. be able e.V. for the project MatchMyMaker, e-NABLE, DDMP (Distributed Design Market Platform), and GIG partners and members, like FieldReady, Communitere Nepal, Cadus e.V., Kumasie Hive, etc. In order to structure all relevant organisations, initiatives and projects, we started to create a “worldwide inventory of organisations and stakeholders active in open healthcare”. This project internal document currently includes over 80 entries.

During the second project year we started to intensify our sustainability planning and have defined a set of opportunities that need to be further elaborated and tested during the second project year. One of the crucial aspects for sustainability is definitely the future funding options, where we currently envision a mix of partnership and donation model combined with crowdfunding for specific careables that would also support other careables-related activities. Our current ideas for these donations and partnership models are mainly based on the assumptions that our

customers are mainly public and private healthcare industry, institutional and private donors. The beneficiaries of careables, namely patients, makers, designers, should mostly be able to use the service freely. Based on the experiences we worked on a first business model that is based on the social business model canvas (described in D5.2 in more detail).

Social Business Model Canvas Social Innovation Lab				
Key Resources - People (Expert Users, Healthcare professionals, Makers, engineers, designers, Trainers, Community and Co-Design Organisers, Legal Experts - Financial means for personal, hosting and maintenance of platform and website - Access to digital fabrication machines <small>What resources will you need to run your activities? People, finance, access?</small>	Key Activities Local - local events that establish collaboration between citizens with disabilities and their families, healthcare professionals and makers: - Open Health Hackademy (Berlin) - MakeHealth Prototyping Series and Wang Trainings (Amsterdam) - HealthCare Summer School and Training for healthcare professionals (Milan) - ambitions in 3 000 hubs Global - general awareness raising campaign through social media - providing inspiring solutions - providing skills and knowledge - facilitating online and offline collaboration and creation of ideas - connecting with other communities and individuals, locally and globally - creating legal guidelines <small>What programme and non-programme activities will your organisation be carrying out?</small>	Type of Intervention Local - events - resources in local languages Global Online Tools: - careables.org Platform - widerapp Open Hardware Repository with Open Healthcare Map and documentation tool - Knowledge Base Materials, e.g. Toolkit for Co-Creation, Trainings on digital fabrication, Legal Guide <small>What is the format of your intervention? Is it a workshop? A service? A product?</small>	Segments - Users/patients and their families - Healthcare professionals - Makers, engineers, designers Beneficiary Customer - healthcare professionals and their employers (hospitals, care homes, manufacturers, health management...) - institutional donors, philanthropic bodies - companies - individuals that are part of the beneficiaries or support them <small>Who are the people or organisations who will pay to address this issue?</small>	Value Proposition - improve quality of life or services through human-centered innovation in healthcare and assistive technology - improve the accessibility of open source products and knowledge to enable innovation beyond the topic of careables Social Value Proposition Impact Measures - impact assessment plan, continuous evaluation of 5 objectives with indicators and a concluding report - methods: qual, walkthroughs, questionnaires, statistics etc. <small>How will you show that you are creating social impact?</small> Customer Value Proposition - reduce the cost of innovation in public healthcare system - fulfil corporate social responsibilities - good feeling for supporting a cause that directly benefit individuals <small>What do your customers want to get out of this initiative?</small>
Partners + Key Stakeholders - careables consortium - patient organisations, associations of disabled people, healthcare providers, hospitals, MedTech industry - maker communities, maker networks, design organisations - philanthropic organisations - platforms with a special focus on health and care related topics <small>Who are the essential groups you will need to involve to deliver your programme? Do you need special access or permissions?</small>	Channels Local - events, meetups, trainings, co-design sessions - ambassadors for health making - resources in local language: on websites of the partners, print materials Global - partnerships - media and social media - direct outreach, applications <small>How are you reaching your beneficiaries and customers?</small>		Revenue - donors, philanthropic bodies - training: fees from participants/their employers - crowdfunding <small>Break down your revenue sources by %</small>	
Cost Structure - biggest expenditure independent of scale: careables platform (server hosting, bandwidth, maintenance) - can be scaled/distributed as funding sources allow: community involvement, trainings and co-creation activities <small>What are your biggest expenditure areas? How do they change as you scale up?</small>	Surplus - any funds that are not reinvested into the platform and into more co-creation activities should go into the creation of more individual careables products <small>Where do you plan to invest your profits?</small>			

Inspired by The Business Model Canvas

Figure 9: Social Business Model Canvas for Careables

The key parameters in this business model relate to the offering of local and global services. Thus, we can also distinguish the calculated cost structures along the expected local and global costs. A first estimation for the next 3 years after the project's EC funding shows the following cost structure:

Activities	Costs			
	2020	2021	2022	TOTAL
Global activities				
careables.org maintainance & hosting	€ 6.000,00	€ 6.300,00	€ 6.615,00	€ 18.915,00
welder.app maintainance & hosting	€ 25.000,00	€ 26.250,00	€ 27.562,50	€ 78.812,50
Global community engagement	€ 60.000,00	€ 63.000,00	€ 66.150,00	€ 189.150,00
TOTAL global costs	€ 91.000,00	€ 95.550,00	€ 100.327,50	€ 286.877,50
Local chapter activities				
HACKademy (3 per year à 20.000€)	€ 60.000,00	€ 63.000,00	€ 66.150,00	€ 189.150,00
Prototyping series (6-8 sessions)	€ 40.000,00	€ 42.000,00	€ 44.100,00	€ 126.100,00
Health & Care Summer School	€ 20.000,00	€ 21.000,00	€ 22.050,00	€ 63.050,00
Legal consultancy	€ 35.000,00	€ 36.750,00	€ 38.587,50	€ 110.337,50
TOTAL local costs	€ 155.000,00	€ 162.750,00	€ 170.887,50	€ 488.637,50
TOTAL ALL Costs	€ 246.000,00	€ 258.300,00	€ 271.215,00	€ 775.515,00

Still, these assumptions are based on the first 18 months; we need to explore and test these options more in the second half of the project.

In terms of funding for these activities we plan to have income mainly via crowdfunding, establishing collaboration agreements with businesses and industry as well as support from institutional donors. The trainings will also be generating some basic income to cover the costs. A detailed overview is provided in D5.2.

There have been no major deviations from the original project plan (Annex 1) for WP5 and no major delay in the submission of the deliverable D5.1. and D5.2.

Summary of achievements WP5:

Table 5: Summary of results WP5

results	indicator of achievement	key lesson
Communication Strategy created	deliverable submitted, including: - local and global outreach strategy - target groups identified, key messages created	- new term "Careables" created - community and communication are closely tied - global outreach needs project results to be effective
Careables visual identity	logos, manuals and templates: version 1, version 2	We recently changed the color design of careables logo and - more

		generally - overall identity for accessibility reasons and to be attractive for a wider target group.
Website published	1st release in month 3 2nd release on 1st October 2019	
Social Media channels created + populated continuously	- followers: Facebook: 410, Twitter: 248, Instagram: 203. - posts: Facebook: 47 in 3 months, Twitter: 484, Instagram: 97. - reach in one month: Facebook: 1.434, Twitter 11.300	- organic reach is increasingly hard to achieve, always mention other communities and people to activate them to share
Presentations about the project	over 60 presentations held at different events during the first 18 months	
Sustainability strategy created	deliverable submitted, including funding and partnership models for Careables activities	- the commitment from the partners is very strong - there are already a number of concrete plans, business models and funding proposals to continue activities around healthcare making after the EU funding period

Outlook WP5:

The planned activities for M18 - M36 are:

- Platform launched – now bigger outreach: coordinated social media campaign with support from all consortium partners, launch of global newsletter, contacting press + media to raise awareness for Open Healthcare solutions
- Organising more workshops, debates and presentations at public events, most prominently: Deasing4Health 2020, MEDICA Düsseldorf, Chaos Communication Congress 2019, re:publica 2020.
- create a Moving Exhibition in Year 3
- Drafting of a White Paper on Legal Guidelines on Open Hardware Healthcare Solutions, in the light of the findings from the research carried out by KUL within WP6 on 'Ethical and Legal Aspects' (and namely, with D6.1 and D6.2).

A few of the current and coming activities within Sustainability:

- Handing in project proposals to foundations: Allianz Foundation, Volkswagen Foundation, Bosch Foundation, Stiftung Charité, Deutsche Telekom Stiftung
- Collaborating with non-profit organisations: Field Ready on the Humanitarian Design Challenge in Nepal, CADUS on the open source life sensor device, Open Source Ecology e.V., Sozialhelden e.V., be able e.V., r0g agency on #ASKotec and #ASKnet
- Working with universities to make Careables part of studies: TU Berlin (Germany), KNUST (Kumasi, Ghana), Fabacademy (international)
- Collaborating with other EU funded projects: Distributed Design Market Platform, Open:Next!, HubIT, DoIT
- Creating strategic partnerships with companies and federations: vdek, Fachverband für Orthopädietechnik und Sanitätshandel Nordost e.V.

1.2.6 Workpackage 6: Legal & Ethical Aspects

Lead partner: KUL

Contributing partners: ZSI, WAAG

WP6 ensures that the applicable legal provisions and ethical considerations are embedded in the design, implementation, and validation of the platform that will be developed. The aim of this workpackage is to provide continuous guidance on the

relevant ethical and legal questions to the consortium members and to produce through gradual refinement a set of legal and ethical guidelines enabling maker communities to develop and share their knowledge in a transparent and legally secure way. In this respect, specific attention is given to an analysis of the applicable rules relating to data protection, liability, and intellectual property.

The ethical and legal guidance provided so far within Made4You focus in the matter of:

- Privacy and Data Protection: this field of law is transversal to the whole project as well as for its exploitation phase, with respect in particular to the following aspects:
 - the careables.org platform and repository must implement and comply with the key principles of data protection law, namely lawfulness, fairness, and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimization; accuracy; storage limitation, integrity and confidentiality as enshrined in art. 5 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)).
 - Co-design and co-creation sessions: the organization of such initiatives must be lawfully performed with respect to the processing of personal data: key legal requirements of GDPR concerning for instance information and consent and the exercise of data subjects rights have to be duly be taken into account by the organisers of events.
 - The careables: The development of the careables themselves, whether entailing in future the processing of personal data, must respect GDPR legal requirements. Of most relevance to this regard are obligations that require to set up secure processing of personal data (as of art. 32 GDPR) and the so-called principle of 'data protection by design' (art. 35 GDPR).
- Intellectual Property law: the co-creation and co-design of open healthcare solutions entail also intellectual property issues, that range from third-party patent protection on certain items to the licensing of project designs within the Carebles.org platform.
- Liability and Tort law: to promote the development of careables and the diffusion thereof, it is of key importance that stakeholders understand their roles and responsibilities from the onset of their involvement. Aspects such as safety and security and the related liability for the reproduction of careables

(such as through fabrication tools or via 3D printing) have been assessed under a liability and tort law perspective.

The importance of legal and ethical guidance in DIY healthcare has also been confirmed by many invitations that KUL, as ethical legal partner, has received for giving talks, presentations at conferences, seminars, workshops etc.[1] These activities include, among others, the Creative Commons Global Summit (Lisbon, 2019)[2]; the Open User Innovation Conference (Utrecht, 2019)[3]; the AAATE Conference - Global Challenges in Assistive Technology: Research, Policy & Practice (Bologna, 2019).[4] In addition, we are working on the dissemination of research results through publication of research findings in high level academic journals related to the field of law and healthcare, or law and innovative technologies (e.g. *Technology and Disability* etc.).

There have been no major deviations from the original project plan (Annex 1) for WP6 and no major delay in the submission of the deliverables D6.1. and D6.2.

Summary of achievements WP6:

Table 6: Summary of results WP6

results	indicator of achievement	key lesson
Report/ Outline of the ethical and legal framework	Project deliverable D6.1 - ' Legal and ethical inventory and in-depth analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Importance of privacy and data protection requirements for development of the Careables.org platform, as well as for Made4You initiatives - Awareness on the necessity to manage IPRs within the Careables.org platform - Awareness on the applicability of the Medical Devices Legal framework for the Careables manufacturers

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness of the existence of ethical principles to be regarded at for the design of the Careables
Report/ Guidelines on the implementation of the identified legal and ethical requirements	Project deliverable D6.2 - 'Implementation of legal and ethical requirements'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PDP requirements must be considered from the early stages of a project - IPRs may be managed by choosing the appropriate OSH licence within the Careables.org - A Careables manufacturer could be subject to the medical devices legal framework under certain circumstances (as described in D6.1 and further detailed in D6.2)

Outlook WP6:

Planned activities (M18-M36): The planned activities of WP6 will be finalised at the drafting of D3.6 - Validation and policy recommendations incl. Guidelines on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). To reach this objective, extensive research on the existing policy related barriers onto the flourishing of co-designed open healthcare solutions will be carried out through literature review on policy-making documents, existing legislation and case law, as well as the attendance of thematic-related events and meetings.

1.2.7 Workpackage 7: Project Management

Lead partner: ZSI

Contributing partners: ALL

This WP is designed to ensure that the results and processes of the project are delivered on time, on budget and with the quality stipulated by the European

Commission. It is also responsible for the project's own IPR and will ensure continuous project quality control and risk management.

No significant changes have occurred during the first year that would put the entire project or specific objectives at risk. All workpackages follow the description of action and the deliverables and milestones have been achieved according to plan.

As a result of the first Meetups and engagement activities the project decided to stress the training aspects of the project and this has led to an increase in engagement from the specific target groups. Thus, this strategy will also be followed during the second half of the project. Overall, the number of events organised or attended by consortium partners is impressive (see Annex).

Administrative management has been concentrating on internal collaboration processes, communication with the EC and other relevant external stakeholders, quality assurance issues and the financial reporting for the period.

In terms of internal collaboration, a structure of regular online as well as face-to-face meetings has been defined. After an initial plan of monthly online meetings the consortium decided to shift to weekly online meetings. All meetings are documented on the internal collaboration platform, which forms the basis for knowledge management and information sharing within the consortium. In addition to the collaboration platform and the weekly skype calls we have also established a Slack channel for internal communication.

The data management plan and project handbook (deliverable D7.1) describes the internal communication and collaboration procedures in detail. It also includes guidelines with regards to data handling, quality assurance and ethical issues. This document is complemented by the deliverables from WP8, which specifically focus on ethical aspects, and the deliverables from WP6, which guide us in terms of legal and ethical aspects.

A Consortium Agreement has been signed before the start of the project amongst all parties defining the rules and obligations across the consortium. Following the structure defined on the consortium agreement representatives for the General Assembly and the Project Management Board (PMB) were assigned at the project kick-off. In addition, an external Advisory Board (AB) has been set up based on the stakeholder analysis in order to have the most relevant stakeholders on board.

The external AB currently consists of the following members:

- Sherry Lassiter, President of Fab Foundation, MIT
- Jon Schull, Co-founder of eNABLE
- David Ott, Global Humanitarian Lab
- Raul Krauthausen, Sozialhelden
- Matilde Leonardi, Director Neurology, Public Health, Disability Unit&Coma Research Centre, Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Neurologico Carlo Besta

The consortium has interacted with all advisory board members, either in face-to-face meetings and/or virtually.

The project management also distributed the signed contract and the advanced payment to the project partners. At the end of the reporting period the partners were advised on how to submit their financial statements to the EC reporting tool.

A contract amendment has been requested during this reporting period. Due to internal restructuring activities partner 5 – MAKEA INDUSTRIES GMBH has requested to leave the project as of 31.12.2018. In order to keep continuity in the project, the consortium agreed to add Agile Heap as a new partner in the project, taking on all tasks and responsibilities of MAKEA INDUSTRIES GMBH. The staff working on the project so far under the umbrella of MAKEA INDUSTRIES GMBH shifted over to Agile Heap and thus a continuity was given for the project. The expertise was kept within the project. Agile Heap took over all tasks from MAKEA INDUSTRIES GMBH as outlined in Annex 1 of the grant agreement, including the leadership of Workpackage 2 and responsibility of Deliverables D2.2, D2.3 and D2.4. as well as Milestone MS3. All parties agreed to the replacement of MAKEA INDUSTRIES GMBH by Agile Heap in all its tasks and responsibilities as of 01.01.2019 and assigning the remaining budget of MAKEA INDUSTRIES GMBH to Agile Heap.

Summary of achievements WP7:

Table 7: Summary of results WP7

results	indicator of achievement	key lesson
solid baseline for collaboration across partners	shared infrastructures; weekly meetings with all partners; every member of the consortium is very active	all individual members of their team make valuable contributions; we need to build on the strengths of individuals

administrative management	all deliverables and financial reporting submitted on time	partners with little ec reporting experience need clear guidelines
Quality assurance	guidelines & templates for reports and deliverables; ethical and legal advice; interaction with the Advisory Board	difficult to get Advisory Board members into a joint meeting; better to engage them individually according to their expertise
Risk management	contract amendment to bring in new partner and cover for the leaving partner	strong commitment from individuals is core

Outlook WP7:

In WP7 we will continue the established processes for collaboration within the consortium and stress the activities towards sustainability.

Also, we will make sure that the results of the first project review will be taken into consideration and implemented accordingly.

The Advisory Board will be strategically consulted, mostly for expanding our community, for establishing collaborations with other initiatives, and for becoming ambassadors for careables. From the experiences in the first 18 Months the interaction with the Board will continue to be on a one-to-one basis and according to their expertise and interests.

1.2.8 Workpackage 8: Ethics Requirements

Lead partner: ZSI

Contributing partners: ALL

The objective of this workpackage is to ensure compliance with the 'ethics requirements' set out by the ethical review.

Being ethically compliant with European regulations and rules is highly important for the project. Thus, we have developed a set of instruments, such as the informed

consent/assent templates or a legal and ethics questionnaire for partners. Apart from these tools and guidelines, active monitoring of ethical requirements is done in close collaboration with WP6.

There have been no major deviations from the original project plan (Annex 1) for WP8 and no major delay in the submission of the deliverable D8.1. and D5.2.

Summary of achievements WP8:

Table 8: Summary of results WP8

results	indicator of achievement	key lesson
achieving ethical compliance	ethical questionnaire informed consent templates data management plan	awareness raising for ethical issues is key for RRI practices

Outlook WP8:

There are no specific deliverables for this WP in the second half of the project. We will continue to follow strict ethical procedures and update the documents in the case of an upcoming need.

1.3. Impact

The information on section 2.1 of the DoA regarding the expected impact of the project is still relevant.

2. Update on the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results

No specific updated to report. The current plans for exploitation and sustainability are described in detail in deliverable D5.2.

3. Update of the data management plan

No specific updates to report. The Data Management plan is included in the deliverable D7.1.

4. Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous reviews

Not applicable; as there has been no previous review.

5. Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2

The main deviation from the original project contract was a change of partner organization in the consortium. The original partner MAKEA left the consortium at the end of the first project year (M12) and was replaced by the new partner AGILE, who took over all tasks and responsibilities. The change in partnership resulted in a contact amendment (**Reference No AMD-780298-6**).

5.1. Tasks

There are no specific deviations to be expected in terms of the technical content of the project.

5.2. Use of resources

The following tables show the person-months reporting for this period (in total and for the individual workpackages), compared to the originally planned use of resources. In the case of relevant deviations, we provide an explanation.

Person-Month Status Table

Table 9: Person-Month Status Table

Workpackage ¹	WP1		WP2		WP3		WP4		WP5		WP6		WP7		TOTAL per Beneficiary	
	Actual WP total	Planned WP total	Actual total	Planned total												

Coordinator ZSI	0,82	2,00	0,24	4,00	0,00	0,00	7,88	12,00	2,43	6,00	0,14	3,00	8,38	18,00	19,89	45
Beneficiary 1 WAAG	14,00	12,00	1,88	10,00	1,17	5,00	0,01	2,00	4,43	10,00	0,03	4,00	0,00	0,00	21,52	43

¹ Please indicate in the table the number of person months over the whole duration for the planned work, for each workpackage by each beneficiary

Beneficiary 2 OPEN	3,37	3,00	4,78	8,00	12,53	19,00	0,29	1,00	3,34	7,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	24,31	38
Beneficiary 3 GIG	1,68	3,00	0,29	6,00	0,71	4,00	0,17	2,00	9,00	18,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	11,85	33
Beneficiary 4 MAKEA	1,00	1,00	5,00	5,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	9,00	9
Beneficiary 5 WEV	1,74	4,00	2,28	2,00	13,23	18,00	3,33	4,00	1,51	4,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	22,09	32

Beneficiary 6 KUL	1,52	2,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,05	2,00	0,44	2,00	8,86	12,00	0,00	0,00	10,87	18
Beneficiary 7 TOG	2,49	5,00	5,03	8,00	2,87	4,00	2,67	6,00	3,00	4,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	16,06	27
Beneficiary 8 AGILE	0,36	2	3,00	8,00	0,07	2,00	0,03	2,00	0,30	2,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	3,76	16

5.3. Overview of Person-months

Table 10: Total number of person-months (planned and reported for Month 18)

	PM	
	planned	total reported (M18)
WP1	34,00	26,98
WP2	51,00	22,50
WP3	53,00	31,58
WP4	32,00	15,43
WP5	54,00	19,00
WP6	19,00	9,03
WP7	18,00	8,38
WP8	0,00	0,00

Please note that for WP8 no person-months were foreseen as this is the obligatory workpackage that has been added during contract preparation to cover the ethical requirements. The efforts for the deliverables of WP8 have been included in WP6 and WP7.

Also note that AGILE entered the project only at the start of the second year and thus their efforts are generally still lower than 50% (as will be shown in the following tables below).

The total amount of planned person-months for this project according to the latest Annex 1 of the contract is 261. The currently reported total amount of person-months at Month 18 is 132,9, which corresponds to 51% of the planned efforts and is thus very well aligned with the contract. While the overall efforts are clearly according to the planning, there are some deviations of efforts in the individual workpackages.

5.3.1. Overview of Person-months for WP1

Table 11: Overview Person-months WP1

WP1 Engagement & Community Growth		
	planned (all)	actual total
ZSI	2,00	0,82
WAAG	12,00	14,00
OPEN	3,00	3,37
GIG	3,00	1,68
MAKEA	1,00	1,00
WEV	4,00	1,74
KUL	2,00	1,52
TOG	5,00	2,49
AGILE	2,00	0,36
TOTAL	34,00	26,98

WP1 has been very active during the first 18 months of the project and this is reflected in the high number of person-months reported. Especially the WP leader, WAAG, has already organised 3 prototyping open calls / series during this period, involving more efforts than originally planned. These activities included tasks from WP1, WP2 and WP5, which were difficult to clearly separate in terms of reporting as they greatly overlap. Thus, for this period WAAG mostly reported their efforts in WP1, however they still have many efforts to draw from other WPs, such as WP2 and WP5.

Similarly, Opendot spent more resources on WP1 than originally planned, as the engagement activities were more resource intensive than expected. However, there is overall more resources available in WP5, which is highly overlapping in activities with WP1 and resources can be drawn from there. The list of events organised or attended by project partners in the Annex of this document gives an overview of the amount of engagement activities performed during this period.

In summary, there is no shortage of efforts for this WP for the next period and partners will continue to contribute to the engagement and community building activities.

5.3.2. Overview of Person-months for WP2

Table 12: Overview Person-months WP2

WP2 Pilot Open Solutions		
	planned (all)	actual total
ZSI	4,00	0,24
WAAG	10,00	1,88
OPEN	8,00	4,78
GIG	6,00	0,29
MAKEA	5,00	5,00
WEV	2,00	2,28
KUL	0,00	0,00
TOG	8,00	5,03
AGILE	8,00	3,00
TOTAL	51,00	22,50

The amount of PM's for wevolver was higher than anticipated, especially for *Task 2.4. Gather insights on co-design and documentation process* because we experienced that many more interviews with users were needed to learn the requirements for the development of the platform in WP3. Initial difficulties that users experienced with early prototypes of the platform required much more support work to enable the co-design sessions to be run. This work provided important input for the developments in WP3.

WP 2 required generally more efforts also for TOG, especially for the following tasks: 1) the definition of careables taxonomy which implies the knowledge and expertise of healthcare professionals about assistive technologies and body functions; 2) the research and selection of existing solutions for people with disabilities and their upload on welder.app.

5.3.3. Overview of Person-months for WP3

Table 13: Overview Person-months WP3

WP3 Platform & Tooling		
	planned (all)	actual total
ZSI	0,00	0,00
WAAG	5,00	1,17

OPEN	19,00	12,53
GIG	4,00	0,71
MAKEA	1,00	1,00
WEV	18,00	13,23
KUL	0,00	0,00
TOG	4,00	2,87
AGILE	2,00	0,07
TOTAL	53,00	31,58

Because the project requires using and testing a working version of the platform, the majority and most difficult parts of the software development needed to be done in the first phase of the project. A half or poorly functioning platform does not enable to host any co-design sessions, nor would it enable relevant learning for future adjustments. The required initial work for the platform includes foundational work on the system architecture (database and server setup), information architecture (platform routing and elemental hierarchy), as well as the majority of the work on user authentication and security. This explains the higher efforts for OPEN and WEV during this first reporting period.

The person-months for TOG were already allocated mainly for the baseline mapping of existing platforms and the definition of personas also by means of a survey

targeted at people with needs, healthcare professionals as well as makers, in close connection with OPEN. Thus, most efforts were spent during this period.

5.3.4. Overview of Person-months for WP4

Table 14: Overview Person-months WP4

WP4 Evaluation & impact assessment		
	planned (all)	actual total
ZSI	12,00	7,88
WAAG	2,00	0,01
OPEN	1,00	0,29
GIG	2,00	0,17
MAKEA	1,00	1,00
WEV	4,00	3,33
KUL	2,00	0,05
TOG	6,00	2,67
AGILE	2,00	0,03
TOTAL	32,00	15,43

WEV needed to ensure that the platform satisfied the requirements and needs of the involved stakeholders. Because the majority of the work in WP3 needed to be done

in the first phase of the project it followed that also the work in WP4 on assessing user-acceptance factors like ease of use accumulated more initial work than expected. End-user input interactively shaped the platform design and functionality.

5.3.5. Overview of Person-months for WP5

Table 15: Overview Person-months WP5

WP5 Dissemination & Outreach		
	planned (all)	actual total
ZSI	6,00	2,43
WAAG	10,00	4,43
OPEN	7,00	3,34
GIG	18,00	9,00
MAKEA	1,00	1,00
WEV	4,00	1,51
KUL	2,00	0,44
TOG	4,00	3,00
AGILE	2,00	0,30
TOTAL	54,00	25,45

TOG exceeded the expected effort in WP5 mainly due to their local communication activities. 3 PMs were already allocated for communication activities on social media and the participations of events. These tasks involve mainly middle profiles (with lower personnel costs than originally planned); thus, the final efforts will probably exceed the person-month number initially planned.

5.3.6. Overview of Person-months for WP6

Table 16: Overview Person-months WP6

WP6 Legal & Ethical Aspects		
	planned (all)	actual total
ZSI	3,00	0,14
WAAG	4,00	0,03
OPEN	0,00	0,00
GIG	0,00	0,00
MAKEA	0,00	0,00
WEV	0,00	0,00
KUL	12,00	8,86
TOG	0,00	0,00
AGILE	0,00	0,00
TOTAL	19,00	9,03

Drafting of deliverables D6.1 Legal and ethical inventory and in-depth analysis (due in M12) and D6.2 Implementation of legal and ethical requirements (due in M18) required additional efforts and consequently more time from KUL mainly because of the new General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). More precisely, the GDPR became applicable as of 25 May 2018. This required additional research to be conducted and more time had to be invested in order to provide clear and concise requirements that are easy to understand by technical partners and end-users within the Consortium. Furthermore, guidelines given by national data protection authorities as well as the EU official bodies were constantly updated and sometimes contradictory or not clear enough which required extra time and efforts for conducting in-depth analysis on the topic. On top of that, case-law concerning this topic was (and still is) becoming bigger and more demanding which requires constant monitoring and research into the topic.

5.3.7. Overview of Person-months for WP7

Table 17: Overview Person-months WP7

WP7 Project Management		
	planned (all)	actual total
ZSI	18,00	8,38
WAAG	0,00	0,00
OPEN	0,00	0,00
GIG	0,00	0,00
MAKEA	0,00	0,00
WEV	0,00	0,00
KUL	0,00	0,00
TOG	0,00	0,00
AGILE	0,00	0,00
TOTAL	18,00	8,38

6. Summary and Outlook

The project team has shown great commitment during the first 18 months to establish careables as an open and inclusive approach to healthcare, and connecting users, healthcare professionals and related stakeholders with actors in digital fabrication, distributed manufacturing and collaborative making. An impressive amount of engagement activities has been performed and we have drawn important lessons learned. The technical development for the platform and its related tools for knowledge sharing and documentation has been driven by real user needs and a co-design process from the onset.

Thus, with the activities of the first 10 months and our continuous reflection and learning we are able to enter the second half of the project with the aim to consolidate our efforts and establish careables as a sustainable service and become the preferred platform for open healthcare worldwide.

7. Annex

The following list includes all project events that were either organized by the project or where consortium partners attended for project dissemination and outreach activities. We distinguish between different types of events:

Table 9: List of events

Event name	Short description	Date	Location	Organiser/ Partner attending	# of par tici pan ts	M A K E R E S E G S E D O U T N P R C H T E K A E A N S T R I I A O O N O Y P N G N

NoordWest hospital MakeHealth workshop.	Waag organised a workshop consisting of an intro to HealthMaking, and a hands-on session to come up with suggestions for improvements. This led to several first prototypes of things that showed room for improvement.	26.1.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	20	x			
Opensource Body	The Makers medialab has invited artists, scientists, healthcare professionals and designers to present and discuss issues regarding DIYbio and open hardware for healthcare. A weeklong festival of workshops, conferences, demos and performances.	27.1.2018	Paris, France	makers, media for labs, Waag	20				x
Hackathon Spaarne Hospital (Presentation about design thinking)	Jurre Ongerling introduced the concept of "making" for Healthcare challenges for the Spaarne Gasthuis Hospital hackathon.	4.2.2018	Haarlem, NL	Spaarne Gasthuis Hospital, Waag	30				x

Spaarne Gasthuis Hackathon	Waag co-organised a 3-day Hackathon in a Hospital in Holland	5.2.2018	Haarlem, NL	Spaarne Gasthuis Hospital, Waag	30	x	x		
Hackathon Spaarne Hospital (General presentation)	Janine Huizenga introduced the concept of "design Thinking" for Healthcare challenges for the Spaarne Gasthuis Hospital hackathon.	5.2.2018	Haarlem	Spaarne Gasthuis, Waag	30				x
City Drivers project event	Laurea-coordinated CityDrivers project aims to improve the ability of creative professionals to provide service design- and co-creation-based services. The event was organised by this project.	13.2.2018	Helsinki	Laurea University of applied science, Waag	50				x
Introduction HVA Students at Waag	presentation of the project to HVA Students	19.2.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	20		x		x
Sensemakers community presentation	presentation of the project	21.2.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	10				x

Help Camp Hackathon	introduction to careables concept and workshop	1.3.-3.3.2018	Kamp Linfort, Germany	Fab Lab Kamplinfort Makea/ Fablab Berlin	50		x			
Meetup Makehealth	MeetUp with the focus on one specific health&care challenge	3.3.2018	Berlin, Germany	Makea/ Fablab Berlin, GIG		x	x			
Hackability@Milano - 1st Meetup	<p>Meetup structure: presentation of general content (call for proposal, tools, user needs, association, best practises, projects) . work in teams around needs/ideas . next steps</p> <p>General content: documentation and presentation of documentation template by Ludovico Russo. 3 teams: 1. documentation of end-part of the cane prototype and test with user (Antonio Lupo) 2. work on a "magnifier" for visually impaired people. The idea is to use an endoscope.</p>	5.3.2018	Milano, Italy	Opendot, Hackability Milano Luiss Hub for makers and students	18		x			

	3. wrist holder for smartphones designed for a TOG child with palsy								
D66 Vrouwen nacht	general project presentation	8.3.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	n.a.				x
Inspiratiedag Noordwest Ziekenhuis	general project presentation	8.3.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	n.a.	x			x
Milano Digital Week	Workshop titled "Why and how to make documentation _ The importance of building communities around ideas" led by Opendot	16.3.2018	Milano, Italy	Opendot	14	x			

	<p>(Enrico Bassi) at Milano Luiss Hub for makers and students.</p> <p>Workshop activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> . presentation of existing platforms on healthcare DIY solutions . assigned task: select a platform and a project within the platform and analyse the provided documentation . fill a form about documentation evaluating clearness, completeness and adding comments/suggestions . team presentations and open discussion about analysed project documentations . assigned task: draft a documentation template 							
<p>Hackability@Milano launching event</p>	<p>Event presenting Hackabilit@Milano. Panelists: Fabio Sgaragli (Fondazione Giacomo Brodolini), Carlo Boccazzi Varotto (Hackability), Enrico Bassi (OpenDot), Paola Pisano (Assessora al Progetto Smart City e innovazione del Comune di Torino), Cristina Tajani (Assessora a Politiche del lavoro, Attività produttive, Commercio e Risorse</p>	<p>22.3.2018</p>	<p>Milano, Italy</p>	<p>Opendot, Hackability, Milano Luiss Hub for makers and students,</p>	<p>40</p>			<p>x</p>

	umane, Comune di Milano), Francesco Torchia (Hackability@Polito), Associazione amici di Paideia(Simone Romano - Hackability@Pininfarina), Studente ITIS Pininfarina di Moncalieri, Luigi Milani (Hackability@Barilla),								
Careables Workshop at Siegen	Fablab Siegen as part of GIG organised a meetup in Siegen. At the moment this focussed on elderly people. Agenda: Intro Careables / Wevolver / Made for my Wheelchair, Introductory Round of Participants, Fablab Tour, Brainstorming - Ideas, Hopes, Expectations, Next Steps / How do we continue?, Feedback	28.3.2018	Siegen, Germany	GIG, Fablab Siegen	11		x		
Waag Meetup handwriting tool	During this Make Health MeetUp, experts explain the opportunities and challenges of 'makeable healthcare' and show inspiring examples. Afterwards we discuss what the impact of this development means for individual situations or professional practice.	19.4.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	15	x	x		

Conference “Fragility into Fragility: Associated Disturbances of Cerebral Palsy in Children, Diagnostic Tests and Therapy”	The 2-day conference involves the main experts in child neuropsychiatry and neurology at Italian and European level. It is targeted to specialists in rehabilitation and aims at improving skills and competences in associated disturbances of cerebral palsy in children. The conference presents the potentials of digital fabrication in customizing healthcare solutions, with the speech of Enrico Bassi on Fondazione TOG's approach with 3d printer, and a special focus on Horizon 2020 project Made4You, Fondazione Tog is a partner of.	21.4.2018	Milano, Italy	TOG	200		x
Maker Gathering „GIG Summit“	Gathering of 80 invited makers, innovators, designers for 3 days as pre-conference for re:publica. Formats: Intro presentations to get to know each other, ideation workshops, brainstorming, knowledge sharing, concluded by the General assembly of the GIG NGO.	29.-30.4. 2018	Berlin, Germany	GIG	80		x

Session at GIG Maker Gathering about Careables	Workshop and discussion with 12 makers from around the world around the specific challenges of making in healthcare as well as documentation of maker projects in general	30.4.2018	Berlin, Germany	GIG	12	x			
1st Careables MeetUp Workshop FabLab Berlin	Introducing the concept of Careables to the FabLab Community, invited stakeholders from disability-related background and interested people. Ideation and rough Prototyping workshop on 5 senses. This was a first start to get people involved. It taught us how much time it would take to explore sessions with attendees. We used "the senses" as a starting point (smelling, tasting, feeling). We created a table working on each document. It is easy to relate to a sense, but it doesn't really work out because many solutions relate to more of a sense, and also the emotional and mental projects are hard to include when talking about the senses.	27.4.2018	Berlin, Germany	Makea/ Fablab Berlin	20	x			

Careables Workshop at re:publica	Introducing the concept of Careables at the re:publica Makerspace. Following a quick introduction and report from the ideation session at Fablab Berlin, there was an exchange of ideas and first prototyping with 12 participants from a wide range of backgrounds	2.5.2018	Berlin, Germany	re:publica, GIG, Makes/Fablab Berlin	13	x		
Transdisciplinary research in Copenhagen	General project presentation of careables	3.5.2018	Copenhagen	Waag	100			x
Made4Wheelchair Workshop at re:publica	Hands-on making session hosted by Isabelle from Fablab Berlin and Daniel from Futurium Berlin as part of the GIG makerspace at re:publica. Participants with wheelchairs and without created wheelchair lighting accessories.	4.5.2018	Berlin, Germany	Re:publica, GIG, Fablab Berlin, be able e.V.	8	x		

Hackability@Milano - 2nd Meetup	Meetup structure: . presentation of general content (call for proposal, tools, user needs, association, best practises, projects) . work in teams around needs/ideas . next steps General content: presentation of Rosa Garofalo, representative of a visually impaired organisation (users profiles, tools provided for those in need) 2 teams work on: 1. Need of visually impaired people: to read and fill in paper document. 2. Redesign the end-part of a cane, starting from a self-made prototype of a user.	4.5.2018	Milano, Italy	Opendot, Hackability, Milano Luiss Hub for makers and students	16	x			
Waag presentation to Anita Chang	Anita Chang from University of Illinois, USA was interested in learning how universities can deploy fablabs in making for health, and what it means to be an open facility. She is Faculty Leader, Collaborative Innovation and the Global Midwest - Humanities Without Walls Research Project at the University of Illinois	9.5.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag Society	2		x	x	

Waag Meetup leg prosthetic	During this MakeHealth meetup we discuss how digital fabrication tools can be applied within healthcare. Together we discover the possibilities of parametric design: a form of design in which sizes can be easily adjusted. We discuss the use of hard- and software to make personalised tools with experts. And we show inspiring examples used in practice. Finally we discuss what the impact of this development means for our own situation and professional practice.	10.5.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag Society	10	x			
Make to care Opentalk	Public talk about projects for people with disabilities connected to maker movement.	14.5.2018	Milano, Italy	Sanofi Genzyme, Opendot, TOG					x
Made4you presentation at TOG	Presentation of Made4You project to a first selected audience of patient's associations, hospitals, caregivers. Made by Antonia Madella and Enrico Bassi. The objective is to engage them in the project (dissemination, co-design sessions, careables platform).	15.5.2018	Milano, Italy	TOG, Opendot	15				x

Waag project Presentation to Russian Makerspace starters	Discussion with a team from Russia about organising hospital hackathons. They wanted to learn from our experiences.	17.5.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag Society	3			x	x
2nd Careables MeetUp Workshop FabLab Berlin	2nd meetup with a slightly changed approach; focusing on a specific need	1.6.2018	Berlin, Germany	Fablab Berlin	12	x			
Torino Mini maker faire	Talk with Enrico Bassi from Opendot: "Digital fabrication for doctors, therapists, and healthcare professionals"	2.6.2018	Torino, Italy	Fablab Torino, OpenDot					x
ECSA 2018 (European Citizen Science Conference)	Short presentation of Careables at a workshop on empowerment and inclusion	4.-5.6. 2018	Geneva, Switzerland	ZSI	40				x

DSI Fair	Within the event organized by Chic project, workshop 6: Collaborative making, frugal technologies, art and creativity - The workshop starts with a short introduction of three CAPS projects: MAZI, OpenMaker, Made4You and from the representatives of Human Ecosystem Relazioni (HER). Each of these teams leads a smaller group discussion addressing challenges and questions around the roles that grassroots, co-design, and collaborative making approaches can play in social innovation and creative practice. The four themes are: Community networks; Art and Creativity; Making and Manufacturing; Healthcare.	6.-7.6. 2018	Rome, Italy	Chic Project, Opendot, TOG	45	x	x			
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Hackability@Milano - 3rd Meetup	<p>Meetup structure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">. presentation of general content (call for proposal, tools, user needs, association, best practices, projects). work in teams around needs/ideas. next steps <p>General content: presentation of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">. Gabriel, Brazilian design student that has created personalized mouse needing some improvements;. mother of Federico looking for a resistant table fitting the child's wheelchair measure. feedback from user testing of his cane. presentation of the magnifier prototype <p>3 teams work on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Gabriel's mouse2. Smartphone holder3. table for Federico	7.6.2018	Milano Luiss Hub for makers and students, Milano, Italy	Opendot, Hackability	20	x		
IDBN - Italian Digital Biomanufacturing Network - 3D Printing and Biomechanics	Within the 3-days congress, presentation of the Made4you project with a talk by Marta Savoldelli.	9.6.2018	Pavia, Italy	Italian Digital Biomanufacturing Network,	50		x	

				TOG					
AHTI presentation during We Make the City	General project presentation of careables	21.6.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	15				x
Workshop with professionals at TOG	<p>The workshop focuses on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">. what co-design means: methods and Tog's experience. introduction on digital fabrication technologies. working group on needs and taxonomy <p>The workshop was addressed to healthcare professionals.</p>	27.6.2018	Milano, Italy	TOG Opendot	8		x		
3rd Careables MeetUp Workshop FabLab Berlin	DIY Hearing Aids with Peggy Sylopp	29.6.2018	Berlin, Germany	Fablab Berlin	18		x		

HACKATHON HACK4EARS	DIY Hearing Aids with Peggy Sylopp	1.-2.7. 2018	Berlin, Germany	Fablab Berlin, Fraunhofer	18	x			
Hackability@M ilano - 4rd Meetup	Meetup structure: . presentation of general content (call for proposal, tools, user needs, association, best practises, projects) . work in teams around needs/ideas . next steps General content: presentation of: . Chenuli, a little baby from Bangladesh by her caregiver. Her little hand has no fingers. Updates about the other projects.	5.7.2018	Milano, Italy	Opendot, Hackability, Milano Luiss Hub for makers and students	15	x			
Creative Industries and Care summer school	Ideation workshop for careables and general presentation of the project	7.5.2018	Antwerp, NL	Waag	100	x			x

Skillshare Workshop // Summer school Maastricht	Educational lecture on co-design for careables and keynote presentation	7.9.2018	Maastricht, NL	Waag	50		x	x
FAB14	During FAB14, Careables presented the following events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> . conference session “Open and inclusive approach to healthcare for citizens based on digital fabrication, distributed manufacturing and collaborative making” by Enrico Bassi . workshop “Easily document a project / Make it comprehensible for (almost) anyone” . workshop “How to Organize Health & Wellbeing-related Meetups?” 	16.7.2018 19.07.2018 8	Toulouse, Auray, France	Opendot, Waag	50			x
Meeting with Associazione Sindrome di Williams	Meeting with Luca Lattuada and Fabiana Gerardi, Associazione Sindrome di Williams. The meeting is a follow up of May event organised by Tog. It aims: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> . to get to know the patient’s organisation and how they work . to collect patients’ needs . to co-design a feasible solution 	24.7.2018	Milano, Italy	Associazione Sindrome di Williams, TOG	2		x	

4th Careables MeetUp Workshop FabLab Berlin	Co-creation workshop	27.7.2018	Berlin, Germany	Fablab Berlin	8	x			
Activating hospitals (Activerende ziekenhuizen)	Presentation at gathering	12.8.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	40			x	x
Zomergasten Presentation Marleen Stikker	In a Nationally televised two hour interview, the Director of Waag spoke of the possibility that patients and professionals have to create their own healthcare solutions. This led to increased interest in the Waag MakeHealth series.	12.8.2018	National Television	Waag	244 000				x
Amsterdam SamenBeter presentatie voor Reframing studio	A collective of Dutch projects and thinkers have gathered under the name of "Samen Beter" (better together) in order to create a local pilot for healthcare provision. In this pilot, individuals will be given the possibility to get a greater influence as healthcare providers themselves. During this event,	15.8.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	25				x

	Machteld Huber was present as well. Her insights are at the foundation of our project.								
5th Careables MeetUp Workshop FabLab Berlin	Co-creation workshop	24.8.2018	Berlin, Germany	Fablab Berlin	12	x			
Open Lights Workshop	Specific co-design workshop targeted towards designs for wheelchair users	24.8.2018	Fablab Dresden, Germany	Fablab Berlin, be able e.V.	10	x			
Design4Health	Conference/workshop: CAREABLES: Co-designing Open Healthcare	4.9.2018	Sheffield	Sheffield, Waag, OpenDot	20	x			x

Rwanda Delegation in Berlin	Presentation about Made4You for a delegation of Rwandan government officials as part of their Study Trip to ICT Research, Education and Business Institutions in Germany. Most interesting lead was discussing to open an open hardware incubator in Kigali, Rwanda to train students to start hardware companies in the country.	6.9.2018	Berlin, Germany	Konnektiv, GIZ, GIG	19				x
Sensemakers community presentation in Amsterdam nr 2	General project presentation of careables	9.19.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	40				x
Humanitarian Makerfaire Kathmandu	Maker Gathering on Humanitarian Innovation and Making, focussing on Health, Education and Environment. Careables hosted a workshop on Making for Health with the Open Source kit #ASKotec and a presentation & discussion titled „Making for Health for the Global South“.	22.-23.9. 2018	Nepal Communitere, Pulchowk	GIG, Communitere Nepal	150			x	

Beyond RCT	General project presentation of careables	9.25.2018	The Circle, ABN Amro	Waag	100	x		x
1st Careables meetup (Opendot)	Meet up structure: . presentation of general content (call for proposal, tools, user needs, association, best practises, projects) . work in teams around needs/ideas . next steps Teams will work on: . Chenuli's litle hand . Local public transport company and low vision disabilities	27.9.2018	Milano, Italy	Opendot, Milano Luiss Hub for makers and students	7	x		
6th Careables MeetUp Workshop FabLab Berlin	Testing Prototypes and gaining Feedback for all Fab Lab Berlin Development Processes	28.9.2018	Berlin, Germany	Fablab Berlin	8	x		

Smart-map final conference	Final event of smart map results presentation. The horizon 2020 project named Smart-map aims to define and implement concrete roadmaps for the responsible development of technologies and services in three key game-changing fields: precision medicine, synthetic biology and 3D printing in biomedicine.	1.10.2018	Brussels, Belgium	ZSI, TOG	25				x
Roessing Research and Development symposium 2018	Roessing Research and Development RRD is the biggest centre in the Netherlands where a wide range of disciplines such as rehabilitation medicine, movement sciences, psychology, physiotherapy, biomedical sciences and computer sciences work together under a single roof on current and future innovations in rehabilitation and chronic care. As an internationally recognised scientific research institute, RRD occupies a unique position between the university and healthcare practice. This event is their annual conference.	10.4.2018	Enschede, NL	Waag	n.a		x		x

Careables - a platform for DIY solutions for Health & Care	Project presentation at maker Faire in Rome	12.10.2018	Rome, Italy	Opendot	50				x
Debby White cane event	Debby is one of the participants of the Made4You event. She hosted a special day to generate more insights into the work that her and her team have been doing.	15.10.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	15	x			x
Grand Challenges Annual Meeting	Booth presenting Fablab Berlin (Makea) with Made for my Wheelchair at big Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation conference	16.-17.10.2018	Berlin, Germany	Fablab Berlin	100				x
Designing a community of care	Conference, presentation	22.10.2018	Eindhoven, NL	Waag	300				x

Big Data and Health	Presentation at workshop	25.10.2018	Eindhoven, NL	Waag	50	x		x
NU.nl media interview Sabine Wildevuur	Interview at national news	25.10.2018	National News Website, NL	Waag	n.a.			x
2nd Careables meetup	Regular meetup at Milano Luiss Hub for makers and students for co-designing solutions for people with need. Topic: public means of transport and visual disability.	25.10.2018	Milano, Italy	Opendot	18		x	
Hacking Female Health Hackathon	With Mentoring from FabLab Berlin Careables Team	2.-4.11.2018	Berlin, Germany	Hacking Health, GIG; Fablab Berlin	8	x		

Extra open night Made4You Teams	At this event, Waag hosted an extra open night to providing working space for teams enrolled in the Made4You program. This event lasted from 17:00 until 21:30	7.11.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	30	x				
Extra open night Made4You Teams	At this event, Waag hosted an extra open night to providing working space for teams enrolled in the Made4You program. This event lasted from 17:00 until 21:30	8.11.2018	NL	Waag	25	x				
Eindhoven SamenBeter presentatie voor Reframing studio	General project presentation of carealbes	14.11.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	40					x
Extra open night Made4You Teams	At this event, Waag hosted an extra open night to providing working space for teams enrolled in the Made4You program. This event lasted from 17:00 until 21:30	20.11.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	20	x				

Introduction Lerarenopleiding at Waag	General project presentation of careables	11.21.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	n.a				x
MakeHealth LiveLab! (three day event)	At the MakeHealth Live Lab! workshop, we invited designers, experiential experts, healthcare professionals, or informal care givers with a great idea for a healthcare solution to be working in a team on a concrete question over a three-day period. This question could be about developing a new solution to a problem or improving an existing tool.	24.- 26.10.2018	Dutch Design Week 2018, Eindhoven, NL	Waag	20	x	x		x
3rd Careables meetup	Regular meetup at Milano Luiss Hub for makers and students for co-designing solutions for people with need.	29.11.2018	Milano, Italy	Opendot	10		x		

Cultura Digitale 4.0 - Futura Mantova	Project presentation for the session <i>Le tecnologie digitali al servizio della disabilità. Mantova verso un laboratorio maker per produrre a favore della disabilità</i> by Marta Savoldelli during Cultura Digitale 4.0 - Futura Mantova. Targets: secondary schools.	30.11.2018	Mantova, Italy	Opendot	80				x
7th Careables MeetUp Workshop FabLab Berlin	regular careables Meetup in Berlin	30.11.2018	Berlin, Germany	Fablab Berlin	18		x		
Extra open night Made4You Teams	At this event, Waag hosted an extra open night to providing working space for teams enrolled in the Made4You program. This event lasted from 17:00 until 21:30	4.12.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	25	x			
re:publica Accra	Ideation Workshop during the conference	14.-15.12.2018	Accra, Ghana	GIG	17		x		x

Presnetatie Theater Zuilen SALTRO	General project presentation of careables	19.12.2018	Utrecht, NL	WAAG	n.a.					x
Chaos Communication Congress	-Presentation about Careables by Fablab Berlin and GIG - Ideation Workshop by GIG, Panel discussion by Fablab Berlin	27.-30.12.2018	Leipzig	GIG, Fab Lab Berlin	50		x			x
Careables presentation to students	Visit at TOG of a secondary school class of students. Topics: rehabilitations, use of technology, co-design of new assistive products, careables.org project	4.5.2019	Milano	TOG	25			x		
Open Light Workshop at Republica	Promoting Careables and building Open°Lights	4.5.2018		Berlin Fablab	16	x	x			

Made series (Open Call) 1.1	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	17.5.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	16	x				x
Made series (Open Call) 1.2	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	24.5.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x				
Made series (Open Call) 1.3	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	5.6.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x				
Made series (Open Call) 1.4	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	7.6.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x				

Made series (Open Call) 1.5	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	14.6.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x						
Made series (Open Call) 1.6	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	21.6.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x						
Made series (Open Call) 1.7	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	28.6.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x						
Made series (Open Call) 1.8	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	5.7.2018	Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x						

Made series (Open Call) 2.1	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	22.09.2018	Contact Makerspace Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x				x
Made series (Open Call) 2.2	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	29.9.2018	Contact Makerspace Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x				
Made series (Open Call) 2.3	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	6.10.2018	Contact Makerspace Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x				
Made series (Open Call) 2.4	4 You	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	20.10.2018	Contact Makerspace Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x				

Made 4 You series (Open Call) 2.5	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	3.11.2018	Contact Makerspace Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x				
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 2.6	Co-creation and co.design sessions based on the open call launched by Waag	10.11.2018	Contact Makerspace Amsterdam, NL	Waag	12	x				
CT2018 networking session	networking session to bring together the different stakeholders (users, makers, donors, healthcare professionals) interested in open healthcare to raise awareness and expand the community; to connect with other initiatives and find partners that support the careables approach.	4.12.2018	Vienna; Austria	ZSI	15					x
re:publica 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 workshops as showcase of the first HackAdemy in Berlin - presentation about Careables - 2 keynotes on stage 1 (1200seats+livestream) 	6.-8.5. 2019	Berlin, Germany	GIG, FabLab Berlin, ZSI	200 0		x			

Hackademy	At the Open Health HACKademy, four interdisciplinary teams with students from different disciplines, people with disabilities and Makers jointly develop open-source hardware solutions, so-called Careables.	1.3.-17.3. 2019	Potsdam, Germany	FabLab Berlin, be able e.V.	24				X
HACKademy Meet Up	Testing first HACKademy Ideas with interested guests after first design sprint	3.2.2019	Potsdam, Germany	FabLab Berlin, be able e.V.	29				x
HACKademy Meet Up	Interim Presentation and Feedback with externals and all interested Guests	9.3.2019	Potsdam, Germany	FabLab Berlin, be able e.V.	31				x
HACKademy Meet Up	Accompany the final presentation of HACKademy	17.3.2019	Potsdam, Germany	FabLab Berlin, be able e.V.	70				x
Creative Commons Summit;	The 2019 Global Summit (9-11 May) runs over 3 full days and features 6 tracks, 120 sessions, 450+ Commoners, 2 evening events. KUL presentation on: Careables - open source hardware in healthcare	9.-11.5. 2019	Lisbon, Portugal	KUL	450				x

Health&care Summer school - Open talk	Opentalk titled "Innovation in healthcare by design and empathy" with 4 special guests: Emanuela Losito from Municipality of Milan, Antonia Madella Noja and Cristina Dornini from TOG Foundation and Greta Castellana from Helix Centre (via Zoom). The main topic was design for empathy presenting 3 different case studies which imply the use of technologies and the co-design approach.	7.6.2019	Opendot, Milano	Opendot together with DDMP project, TOG	30				x
The 17th International Open and User Innovation Conference	The 17th International Open and User Innovation Conference, July 8-10, 2019, Utrecht University School of Economics. KUL presentation on: Careables – end user innovation for open DIY healthcare solutions	9.7.2019	Utrecht, NL	KUL	app 200				x
AAATE 2019	AAATE 2019 Conference - Global Challenges in Assistive Technology: Research, Policy & Practice, August 27-30, Bologna. KUL presentation on: 'Sharing is caring': what are the main legal and ethical challenges to be looked at when co-designing assistive technologies? AAATE - Association for the Advancement of Assistive Technology in Europe	30.8.2019	Bologna, Italy	KUL	app 200				x

Health&Care Summer School	<p>The Health&Care Summer School focuses on "Design for care" with the aim of developing concrete and simple solutions for the needs of people with disabilities. The Health&Care Summer School has 14 participants and foresees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> / lectures in compelling topics such as co-design methodology, design for all, storytelling vs storytelling, the importance of aesthetics / teamwork co-design: practical sessions for multidisciplinary teams working together with need-knowers / training on digital fabrication technologies 	8-9.6. and 22.-23.6. 2019	Milano, Italy	Opendot (within DDMP project)	22	x	x			
Fab15	<p>International Conference held in Egypt. 3 Careables events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> . presentation to the Assistive Technologies Working group . FAB blast - careables presentation . workshop "Co-design and share that help people with disabilities" 	28.7.-2.8.2019	El Gouna, Kairo, Egypt	Opendot, Waag	200					X

User centred design (UXD) Healthcare Amsterdam	2-day conference covering the latest and greatest in User-Centered Design in Healthcare. Careables and co-design methodology presentation by Alessandro Masserdotti (Opendot)	4-5.07.2019	Amsterdam	Opendot	100					x
Open Know-How Summit	Careables presentation	11-12.07.2019	Warsaw	Makernet alliance, Opendot	15					
Communities & Technologies 2019	International conference; presentation	3.-7.6.2019	Vienna, Austria	ZSI, GIG	80					X
maker Faire Vienna	national maker faire; attracts a lot of families over the weekend; ZSI had a hands-on stand for children to create their own lightbox; careables folders were distributed	4.-5.5.2019	Vienna, Austria	ZSI	10000					x
I Giovedì della salute	A series of 4 events within the exhibition "999. Una collezione di domande sull'abitare contemporaneo"	20.1.2018	Triennale di Milano, Italy	Opendot and Sanofi Genzyme, TOG	25					X

	<p>First topic: How to get better the quality of life of people?</p> <p>"MakeToCare" with Sanofi Genzyme, winners of Make to care contest 2017, OpenDot, Fondazione TOG and Stefano Maffei / Polifactory</p>								
I Giovedì della salute	<p>A series of 4 events within the exhibition "999. Una collezione di domande sull'abitare contemporaneo"</p> <p>"(Con)vivere con l'Artrite Reumatoide" (Living with rheumatoid arthritis) with Sanofi Italia, OpenDot, Antonella Celano e Angela Lorè / APMAR, Ugo Viora / ANMAR, Leoni Fischer</p>	8.2. 2018	Triennale di Milano, Italy	Opendot and Sanofi Genzyme	20				x
I Giovedì della salute	<p>A series of 4 events within the exhibition "999. Una collezione di domande sull'abitare contemporaneo"</p> <p>"Ben oltre la pelle. (Con)vivere con la Dermatite Atopica" (Beyond the skin. To live with atopic dermatitis) with Sanofi Genzyme,</p>	22.3 2018	Triennale di Milano, Italy	Opendot and Sanofi Genzyme	25				x

	ANDeA, Federasma, Progetto ICARO, Paolo Pigatto / Ospedale Gian Galeazzi, Dotdotdot, Empatica								
I Giovedì della salute	<p>a series of 4 events within the exhibition "999. Una collezione di domande sull'abitare contemporaneo"</p> <p>"Il significato di vivere una vita rara" (The meaning of living a rare life) with Sanofi Genzyme, Tommasina Iorno / FIMR, Alessandra Airoidi / X Fragile Onlus, Maria Domenica Cappellini / Policlinico di Milano, Pierfrancesco Majorino / Comune di Milano and Fabio Gorrasi</p>	28.3.2018	Triennale di Milano, Italy	Opendot and Sanofi Genzyme	25				x
Meeting Ospedale Paolo with San Paolo	Together to Go Foundation's activities presentation with a focus on an application of digital fabrication technologies for rehabilitation and Made4You project	7.3.2018	Milano, Italy	TOG	10	x			

MakeToCare, un ecosistema emergente nel campo dell'healthcare - presentazione	The MakeToCare report represents the result of a mapping and research initiative about innovative healthcare projects developed by Polifactory in collaboration with Fondazione Politecnico, sustained by Sanofi Genzyme. One of the case studies is Tog and Opendot project of assistive devices.	21.2. 2018	Milano, Italy	Fondazione Bassetti, TOG	30					x
Meeting with Officina Ortopedica	Presentation of TOG activities with a focus on application of digital fabrication technologies for rehabilitation and Made4You project	23.2. 2018	Milano, Italy	TOG	4	x				
Meeting with Fondazione Bassetti	Presentation of made4You project and TOG activities (careables/3d printer)	10.4. 2018	Milano, Italy	TOG	10	x				
Exposanità	Fair about healthcare products/assistive devices	19.4. 2018	Exposanità, Milano, Italy	TOG, Opendot	15					x

Careables presentation to students	Visit at TOG of a secondary school class of students. Topics: rehabilitations, use of technology,co-design of new assistive products, careables.org project	3.5. 2019	Milano, Italy	TOG	24	x			
Meeting with IED students	Visit at TOG and presentation of co-design approach in the creation of careables	14.3. 2019	Milano, Italy	TOG	3	x			
Co-designing careables – meeting with NABA students	Presentation of the brief concept to a group of 6 students. For the university exam they are going to develop a careable for Tog children connected to psychomotor education	19.03.2019	Milano, Italy	TOG	6	x			
Reprocity Design.Liege	Triennale of design: exhibitions, events. The Handle with Care section explores the tensions that arise when design confronts human well-being. Objects, spaces, graphics, and services, engage and affect our bodies, minds, and even our spirits. Often their design promises transformation, for us, and others, impacting on our relationships. They	5.10.2018/ 25.11.201 8	Various locations in Province de Liege, Belgium	Opendot, TOG	n.a.				x

	can also serve as a witness to our vision(s) of medical conditions, normality and vulnerability. On display: Glifo and la bicicletta di ognuno by Opendot and TOG								
Makers empowering education	2nd FabLearn Conference in Israel. Topic: how Makers provide innovative learning solutions for serious educational challenges! An event led by the Transformative Learning Tech Lab (Stanford University).	6.11.2018	Zoa House - Tel Aviv	Fab learn, Opendot	200				x
Training course at Niguarda Hospital	Introduction to digital fabrication technologies	17.12.2018	Niguarda Hospital	Niguarda Hospital, Opendot, TOG	15		x		
Presentation at Politecnico di Milano	Carebles presentation to students	19.3. 2019	Politecnico di Milano, Italy	Politecnico di Milano, Opendot, TOG	30				x

Presentation at Politecnico di Milano	Careables presentation to students	5.4. 2019	Politecnico di Milano, Italy	Politecnico di Milano, Opendot, TOG	30				x
Design in the age of experience	Careables presentation at Solidworks event	10.4. 2019	Milano, Italy	SuperStudio Più, Milano, Opendot, TOG	20				x
Design Collisions	The exhibition (at Salone del Mobile/ Dererum Natura - curated by Laura Traldi) shows the activating power of design in the development of collective intelligence to tackle contemporary issues. On display Unico – The Other Design.	5.-14.4. 2019	Milano, Italy	Cascina Cuccagna, Milano, Opendot, TOG	n.a.				x
Careables on Air #1	A double interview on a monthly basis to map, learn and discuss what is happening in Italy and around the world in the health & care sector. The event features stories of people with concrete projects and solutions of Design for Care.	14.4.2019	Cascina Cuccagna, Milano, Italy	Opendot, TOG	8				x

	The first event is in the framework of Design Collisions exhibition and presents the relation between design and healthcare. Three speakers: Cristina Dornini, Antonia Madella Noja and Laura Traldi.								
Careables on Air #2	The event is a double interview and features stories of people developing projects in the field of healthcare by means of digital fabrication technologies. 2 speakers: Nadia Crivelli, occupational therapist and Alessandro Terrani, researcher.	20.5. 2019	Niguarda Hospital, Milano, Italy	Opendot	10				x
Careables presentation	Meeting with Buzzi healthcare professionals about careables and possible projects to work on	16.4.2019	Buzzi Hospital, Milano, Italy	Opendot	10				x
Digital fabrication technologies – training course for healthcare professionals	Workshop in collaboration with Buzzi Hospital about potentials of digital fabrication technologies	21.5. 2019	Milano, Italy	Opendot	5	x			

3d printing and innovative technologies for the creation of solutions	Training course in collaboration with Affidabile. It is targeted to occupational therapists and healthcare professionals.	25.5 2019	Affidabile, Milano, Italy	Opendot	36		x			
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[1] The exhaustive list of dissemination initiatives and events will be provided in D5.4 – ‘Final Dissemination and Sustainability Report’ (M36).

[2]<https://ccglobalsummit2019lisbonportugal.sched.com/event/MjHI/how-open-is-distributed-design-an-overview-about-the-distributed-design-market-platform-and-its-activities>.

[3] <https://sites.google.com/view/oui2019/>.

[4] <https://aaate2019.eu/>.